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Ancient Uzbek Ways of Decorating Clothes: Traditions and Symbolism

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***Abstract:** In this article, we will look at a few key aspects of the ancient Uzbek traditions of clothing decoration.*

***Key words:** Textiles and embroidery, traditions and craftsmanship, Atlas, Adras, Goldsmithing.*

Ancient Uzbek decorative ways: traditions and craftsmanship

Uzbekistan, with its centuries-old history and diverse culture, is known for its unique decorative traditions, which were formed at the crossroads of trade routes, cultures and religions. Ancient Uzbek decorative techniques, passed down from generation to generation, are a vivid reflection of the rich heritage of the country and its people. In this article, we will look at a few key elements of Uzbek decorative arts.

The ancient Uzbek ways of decorating clothes represent a rich heritage that combines beauty, art and symbolism. These traditions not only reflect the cultural characteristics of Uzbekistan, but also convey deep historical and social meanings. From embroidery and fabrics to accessories and jewellery, every detail in Uzbek clothing carries part of the country's unique cultural identity.

Textiles and embroidery

Textile art in Uzbekistan has a long tradition, and Uzbek textiles and embroidery are some of the most striking examples of decorative craftsmanship. ‘Suzani’ - is a traditional Uzbek embroidery that is made from bright and intricate patterns that symbolise different aspects of life and nature. Suzani is often used to decorate walls, cushions, blankets and clothing.

‘Adras’ is another unique type of Uzbek textile. This fabric, made from silk and cotton, is decorated with colored stripes and patterns. Adras is often used to create traditional outfits and home décor.

The word "Atlas" means flat, smooth when translated from Arabic. It is a single-faced smooth fabric made from natural silk, both warp and weft.

Specially processed, the satin is given a shine, so it is polished. The best type of satin woven from natural silk is called eight-threaded satin. The whole secret of Khonatlas lies in its construction and weaving method.

Atlas weaving has been developed in Margilon for a long time and has spread to other places. At the beginning of the 20th century, there were many satin weavers here.

A special cut in satin weaving. In the places where the Tanda threads cover the warp threads, they do not lie on each other, but several threads move.

The number of warp and weft threads in rapport is at least five. The surface of gauzes woven with satin weaving is smooth, and only the places where they cover the threads of argoq or tanda look long. If on the surface of the gauze, the yarns of the yarn cover the threads of the body, such gauze is called the satin or satin of the yarn. If, on the surface of the gauze, tanda threads cover more of the jute threads, such gauze is called tanda satin or satin.

Adras-tanda is a gauze made of natural silk, and arka is made of thick thread. Because the flower is double-sided, in some places it is called duroya. As a result of fermentation, one side of high-quality adras is smooth as satin, and the other side is rough. The flowers are arranged in an abr pattern, and yellow, blue, pink, and red colors are used.

Until the 1920s, Adras was woven in Margilon, Khojand, Bukhara, Samarkand and other places, and was sold not only in Central Asian markets, but also in neighboring countries such as Afghanistan and China.

Among the silk fabrics, the most popular are clouded satin and satin. Their uniqueness is that decorations and flowers are drawn not on the fabric, but on the weaving thread itself. For example, 3,600 silk threads need to be combined to weave a 200-meter-long, 40-centimeter-wide satin. Even if one fiber is broken, the quality of the product will be affected. Therefore, it is very difficult to add a new element to the fabric. Dyeing threads in the "abr" method also requires great skill. It is important to note that all colors are made in a natural way, from dye-giving herbs. Therefore, they do not lose their quality, colors do not mix.

Women's dresses, blankets, blankets, men's coats and other items are made from satin. Along with women's clothes, cloaks, blankets, and blankets are made from Adras.

There are many popular types of atlas and adras, and now there are dozens of types of atlas and adras. These are the following:

“Marg’ilon”, “Navro‘z”, “Rasadxona”, “Bibixonim” “Nog‘ora”, “Kiprik”, “Qirolicha”, “Panja”, “Kelinchak”, “Qora atlas”, “Bargi karam”, “Chaqirim”, “Yahudiy nusxa”, “Namozshomgul”, “Shaxmat”, “Qora ko‘zim”.

Nowadays, the art of weaving our national fabrics is developing rapidly. "Decree on further support for development" is an important factor in the development of this field. In addition, many dresses are created from satin and adras, combining nationalism and modernity. You can find different types of dresses like this today.

1.photos. Kinittig of "Atlas" and "Adras"

2.photo. "Atlas" 3.photo. "Adras"

Goldsmithing is a type of decorative art; a branch of applied art that creates ornaments by embroidering with gold (gold and silver) thread, fine wire, and silk. Velvet, silk, movut, leather, etc., mounted on a square belt (korchop). embroidery (flower, pattern, picture) is sewn on fabrics in the goldsmithing method. Sometimes metal, stone, glass beads are also used in embroidery, they are made of various fabrics (velvet, silk, etc.). Pre-made (copy of a sculpture created by artists) paper is widely used. The paper reinforced (stitched or glued) to the fabric is covered with darning thread on one side (for the strengthening seam, oil-colored thread is used for the darning thread), as a result, the surface of the pattern is covered with darning threads, and only the pattern of the pattern is formed on the reverse side of the fabric. Goldsmiths use several methods to create ornaments: zaradozi zamindozi and zaradozi guldozi, as well as birishimdozi (when silk is used), pulakdozi (when button-like metal leaves are used), etc. The skillful use of several types of reinforcing and editing seams and their combination with the embodiment of the pattern gives charm and sophistication to gold jewelry; their artistic value depends on the embodiment of the pattern, raw materials, stitching, and the taste and skill of the goldsmith. A widespread tradition in the embodiment of pattern as a type of artistic craft is widespread in the Near and Middle East.

Craftsmen engaged in goldsmithing, both in ancient times and now, are called "goldsmiths". The embroidery of Uzbekistan cannot be fully imagined without the unique art of goldsmithing. This art flourished in Bukhara in the middle of the last century. There, in the workshops of the emir's palace, skilled artisans decorated the sumptuous clothes worn by the emir and his courtiers. Goldsmithing usually belonged to men and they passed their craft on to their children. The art of goldsmithing has a long history, and almost all Eastern countries are considered its homeland. The traditions of the art of goldsmithing existed and were popular in their time. In today's Iran, the examples of goldsmithing from the 15th-17th centuries have been preserved.

Almost all Bukhara goldsmith's items were used for the needs of the emir's palace, only a very small amount was put on the market for sale. At that time, only people belonging to the Khan and his blood relatives wore men's clothes made of zar. No one, not even one of the highest officials, had the right to order these expensive clothes. They could wear these clothes only when the emir gave them as a gift. Only members of wealthy households had the right to wear gold-plated clothes for women and children. Men's tunics, turbans, hats, trousers, shoes, women's dresses, vests, shorts, headscarves, scarves, boots and shoes are sewn with dice and silver thread.

Since the day we gained independence, the entire policy of our country has been focused on restoring and strengthening our identity. Especially in the formation of such a sacred feeling in our youth, who are the future of our country, our national craftsmanship plays an important role along with our mother tongue, traditions and customs.

On March 31, 1997, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to support the further development of folk crafts and applied arts by means of the state" was announced. Based on the decree, the "Hunarmand" Republican Association was established and its regional branches were opened in the regions. The purpose of the organization of this association and its regional divisions was to restore the folk arts and crafts, which had been forgotten for many years, and to introduce the Uzbek national arts and crafts to the whole world.

Goldsmithing is an interesting and creative work that can bring a lot of joy to a person, can be a pastime in his free time, and can bring a person to the world of sophistication. When mastering the methods of dicing, everything may not turn out well at once, because goldsmithing requires patience, attention, order. It is necessary to be patient. As you acquire the necessary skills, the job will gradually become easier.

4.photos. process of "Goldsmithing"

Embroidery — the profession of embroidery, the qad of Applied Art. one of the areas. Archaeological finds are found in almost all chawks of embroidery.shows that in connection with the climate, natural

conditions, mult, the culture, art of each people, along with the types of professions, have developed under their influence. The appearance of embroidery is associated with the occurrence of ties and seams on clothes made of leather. During the periods, with the transition from stone to bone bigiz, from it to metal bigiz, as well as weaving, weaving fabric, dyeing, etc. works. See the progress of embroidery. It can be observed in the image of Asian, European, American cultural monuments, embroidery in literary sources, as well as in preserved embroidery samples. The most difficult of embroidery products. no copies have been preserved. In the peoples where embroidery developed, it was influenced by Fine Arts. English embroidery dating from the 11th century features battle plaques. Russian embroidery from the 12th century shows the influence of Byzantine icon art. Embroidery shows from the 14th century in China, known as "syuxua" (needle image), are stylistically close to the landscape genre, which is made with a dream.

Embroidery in Europe rose to the top during the Renaissance. The great artists of the era (mas, Perujino, Botticelli, and b.1975) were the most influential artists of the period.) made andases for embroidery, which increased the artistry of embroidery. In embroidery, precious stones were also used, yarn, wool, silk, zar and silver water were given. In Europe in the 18th century, embroidery items made using embroidery were common in the decoration of noble clothing.

With the invention of the embroidery machine in the 2nd half of the 19th century, embroidery enterprises began to emerge in countries with the development of the industry, i.ch.ni the launch brought traditional embroidery into crisis. The existing traditions in embroidery faded, cheap price machine embroidery squeezed out large denominators and labor-intensive hand embroidery. But in several countries, along with machine embroidery, special attention is paid to manual embroidery, the work of embroidery is in decorating museums, public buildings.

Qad of embroidery products in Central Asia. Hilary is barely preserved. Art objects and embroidery in museums, such as palak, sozana, linen, kirpech, zardevor, belong only to the 19th century.

Miniatures in books dating from the 14th and 15th centuries indicate that embroidery has been widely developed here since ancient times. In particular, Rui González de Clavijo, the Spanish ambassador who lived in the Palace of Amir Temür, wrote in his memoirs that he watched embroidery ornaments at the palace. Behzod also featured an embroidered tent in the miniature "Timur on the throne" (1467), which he worked on the manuscript of the "triumphal".

Embroidery is common in Central Asia, especially among Uzbek, Turkmen, Tajik women. Clothes are made in the family, art objects (sozana, kirpech, dorpech, linen, oynahalta, teahalta, etc.) 's main parts were made in each household itself.

Embroidery stitches, embroidery and a variety of styles indicate the great art of Uzbek embroidery. Mas, Nurota, Bukhara, Samarkand embroidery products are sewn with more diaper stitches, in the Prince's diaper, Kandahar, Iraqi, and in Tashkent with more printed stitches. The changes that took place in social life influenced the traditions of embroidery, the types of products. For example, now objects such as strangoma, dorpech, oynahalta have lost their significance, clothes such as paranji, bitch can only be found in museums. Art objects and objects such as doppies, bags, nimcha, kavush, kirpech, sozana have undergone great changes in their form and artistic decoration, being decorated with modern taste. Uzbek embroidery is common in the decoration of the item from patterns of other types of Applied decorative art, and plant-like images, horns, gulbands, bouquets are common in embroidery. In the embodiment of the pattern, the main decoration is in the middle of the fabric, and the borders are an additional decoration. But there are also a lot of embroidery, in which the border decoration is skillfully worked. The use of islimium flower (patterns) found in embroidery, wood

carving, candling, embroidery also shows that the drawing (patterns) have prepared drawings (patterns) in various fields of Applied decorative art. On the basis of patterns (flowers) created by draftsmen in embroidery, embroidery creates an art object. The main working weapons used in embroidery are: needle, needle with loops, bigiz with loops, angishvona, chambarak and B.; common types of chok: print, kandayal, chindayal, khomdozi, yurma, Iraqi popur, hanger and bakhya.

5.photos. Types of "Embroidery"

6.photo. "Embroidered fabric pillow"

7.photo. "Emroidery" process

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